

1 **Review**

2 **Telemedicine in Neurological Disorders: Opportunities and Challenges**

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18

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29

30 **ABSTRACT**

31 **Introduction:** Telemedicine represents an emerging model for the assessment and management
32 of various neurological disorders.

33 **Methods:** We sought to discuss opportunities and challenges for the integration of telemedicine
34 in the management of common and uncommon neurological disorders by reviewing and
35 appraising studies that evaluate telemedicine as a means to facilitate the access to care, deliver
36 highly specialized visits, diagnostic consultations, rehabilitation, and remote monitoring of
37 neurological disorders.

38 **Results:** Opportunities for telemedicine in neurological disorders include the replacement of or
39 complement to in-office evaluations, decreased time between follow-up visits, reduction in
40 disparities in access to healthcare, and promotion of education and training through interactions
41 between primary care physicians and tertiary referral centers. Critical challenges include the
42 integration of the systems for data monitoring with an easy-to-use, secure, and cost-effective
43 platform that is both widely adopted by patients and health-care systems and embraced by
44 international scientific societies.

45 **Conclusions:** Multiple applications may spawn from a model based on digitalized healthcare
46 services. Integrated efforts from multiple stakeholders will be required to develop an
47 interoperable software platform capable of providing not only a holistic approach to care but also
48 one that reduces disparities in the access to care.

49

50 **1. INTRODUCTION**

51 As videoconferencing has become ubiquitous across the private and public sectors, telemedicine
52 has also arisen at the forefront of clinical care. This technology has the potential to augment in-
53 office evaluations, minimize disparities in access to healthcare, and decrease the amount of time
54 between follow-up visits.¹ These benefits ultimately stand to redesign the clinical workflow,
55 which may streamline the management of complex medical conditions between tertiary referral
56 centers and primary care physicians.²

57

58 **2. METHODS**

59 We sought to critically assess opportunities and challenges for telemedicine in neurological
60 disorders. Telemedicine was defined as an interface in a virtual patient-physician relationship in
61 order to provide primary and secondary care in neurodegenerative, cerebrovascular, neuro-
62 oncological, and neuroinflammatory disorders; assist the remote management of deep brain
63 stimulation (DBS), transcranial direct current stimulation (tCDS), and infusion pumps; deliver
64 highly specialized visits (telegenetics), diagnostic consultations (teleradiology and
65 telepathology), or rehabilitative programs (telerehabilitation); and monitor motor and non-motor
66 functions in an ecologically valid environment (telemetry). Attention was devoted to the
67 challenges associated with the integration of telemedicine into innovative models of care.

68 We considered articles involving human subjects published in English and indexed in PubMed
69 between January 2000 and January 2018. Our MESH search terms included “telemedicine”,
70 “telehealth”, “aging disorders”, “cerebrovascular diseases”, “stroke”, “hypertension”, “diabetes”,
71 “oncology”, “neurooncology”, “multiple sclerosis”, “Parkinson’s disease”, “deep brain
72 stimulation”, “infusion systems”, “transcranial stimulation”, “genetics”, “diagnosis”, “EEG”,
73 “telemetry”, and “rehabilitation”. No restrictions were applied to gender, age, ethnicity, disease
74 duration, or disease severity. The reference lists were additionally screened for pertinent studies
75 not included in the original searching strategy. Abstracts were independently reviewed for
76 eligibility criteria by one author and validated by at least one additional author. Relevant articles
77 ([Figure 1](#) and [Table 1](#)) were analyzed according to the following themes: “Opportunities” and
78 “Challenges” ([Figure 2](#)).

79 **3. OPPORTUNITIES**

80

81 **3.1 Management of diseases with high social-impact**

82

83 3.1.1 Aging disorders

84 Life expectancy is projected to increase dramatically in the ensuing decades demanding careful
85 reallocation of health care resources.³ Telemedicine may offer a model by which to defray these
86 expenditures for diseases related to aging, including dementia and other neurodegenerative
87 disorders.² Specifically, video-based telehealth visits may mitigate burdensome and costly
88 transportation needs and also reduce waiting times for all stakeholders. The latter benefit may
89 then aid in longitudinal, continuous monitoring while potentially increasing the ecological
90 validity of the clinical picture.⁴

91 In a randomized controlled trial (RCT) of elderly homebound individuals,⁵ a telehealth care
92 model delivered by trained nurses was compared to the standard of care of in-home nursing care.
93 The telehealth model included daily acquisition of symptoms, body weight, sessions of problem-
94 solving treatment for comorbid depression, and consultations with primary care physicians for
95 changes in the treatment plan for chronic diseases. This study demonstrated that integrated
96 telehealth service improved symptoms and reduced the number of emergency department visits
97 in elderly patients with chronic diseases and depression.⁵

98

99 3.1.2 Cerebrovascular disorders

100 Cerebrovascular disorders require periodic evaluations to check efficacy, dose, and side effects
101 of medications. Mobile- and web- based platforms have been leveraged in the secondary and
102 tertiary prevention of these conditions with the goal of encouraging self-monitoring of
103 hypertension, body weight, waist circumference, blood lipid profile, smoking, and glycemia.^{6,7}
104 Randomized controlled studies suggest that home blood pressure monitoring may result in lower
105 morbidity and mortality when compared to standard office visits.⁸⁻¹⁴ Moreover, a meta-analysis
106 showed that home blood pressure telemonitoring improves hypertension and associated
107 healthcare outcomes, although more expensive than the usual standard of care.¹⁴ A few trials

108 utilized telemedicine to improve glycemic control in patients with types I and II diabetes
109 mellitus.¹⁵⁻¹⁷ In these cases, telemedicine was delivered through video conferencing, web-based
110 educational sessions, and remote contact with healthcare professionals, as well as frequent
111 monitoring of blood glucose levels, body weight and blood pressure.¹⁸

112

113 3.1.3 Neuro-oncological disorders

114 Teleoncology, an emerging model for the remote management of oncological disorders, has
115 already been employed in high-income countries with vast territories, such as the United
116 States,^{19,20} Canada²¹ and Australia.²² Teleoncology may serve multiple needs. First, to create
117 virtual tumor boards between physicians operating in underserved areas and tertiary referral
118 centers.^{19,23} Second, to guarantee access to genetic counseling, which is becoming the foundation
119 of "precision-medicine"-based therapeutic approaches.²⁴ Third, to improve the primary and
120 secondary prevention of cancer. Fourth, to offer the possibility to patients living in rural areas to
121 be enrolled in RCT.¹⁹ Fifth, to limit the impact of follow-up visits in the increasing population of
122 cancer survivors. Traditional models require patients to travel from their homes to cancer centers
123 for face-to-face evaluations. Innovative models suggest that routine follow-up visits can be
124 conducted via telemedicine without undermining the patient satisfaction or compromising the
125 clinical outcomes.²⁵⁻²⁷ And sixth, teleoncology addresses one of the critical unmet needs for the
126 management of advanced-stage cancer, namely the feeling of abandonment associated with the
127 transition from an active phase of cancer-fighting treatment to a passive phase of in-hospice
128 palliative care.²⁸ Moreover, teleoncology has the potential to address social and geographical
129 disparities associated with uneven wealth and health care distribution in the era of globalization.
130 While cancer mortality rates are decreasing in developed countries,²⁹ significant differences
131 persist within select areas of the world.³⁰ The incorrect risk stratification and the scarcity of
132 standardized treatment protocols contribute to the different survival rates observed.³¹ Of note, in
133 the field of pediatric brain tumors in India, it has been clearly shown that more than 25% of
134 patients abandoned treatment as a consequence of late diagnosis, complex multidisciplinary
135 treatment involved, and lack of uniformity management between different oncology centers.³²
136 Within this context, telemedicine might facilitate communication between advanced oncological
137 Centers and local primary care facilities, as demonstrated by successful initiatives in children

138 with cancer and other catastrophic diseases conducted in low-middle income countries.^{33,34}
139 Strategic investments in innovative model of care could significantly improve different fields of
140 oncology, and particularly of neuro-oncology.³⁵⁻³⁸ To date, studies on tele-neuro-oncology are
141 mostly limited to the pediatric population.³⁵⁻³⁸ The success in this particular age group, however,
142 brings the promise to improve the management of primary and secondary cerebral tumors in the
143 entire population of patients with oncological disorders.

144

145 3.1.4 Multiple sclerosis

146 The successful management of patients with multiple sclerosis (MS) requires adherence to
147 disease-modifying therapies (DMTs), individualized approach for patient-reported symptoms,
148 and adequate control of disease comorbidities such as fatigue, depression, and cognitive
149 impairment. Telemedicine has the potential to improve adherence to DMTs³⁹ and management of
150 debilitating symptoms such as fatigue. An open-label study combining telemonitoring and
151 remote coaching detected favorable effects on fatigue in MS.⁴⁰ A small RCT showed the
152 feasibility and effectiveness of telephone-based, teleconference, or web-based interventions in
153 increasing physical activity and reducing MS-related fatigue.⁴¹⁻⁴⁴ Settle and colleagues reported
154 the feasibility of automated neuropsychological assessments using internet-based application
155 from the home environment of patients with MS,⁴⁵ Mohr and colleagues administered telephone-
156 based cognitive behavioral therapy for the treatment of MS-related depression,^{46,47} and Charvet
157 and colleagues used a web-based, remotely supervised adaptive cognitive remediation
158 intervention in MS.^{48,49} Virtual reality has been also employed to administer physiotherapy and
159 in-home rehabilitation with results comparable to in-person physical therapy.^{50,51}

160

161 **3.2 Remote management of neurological disorders from high-specialized Centers**

162

163 3.2.2 Deep Brain Stimulation, Infusion Systems, and Transcranial Direct Current Stimulation

164 While cost-effectiveness of deep brain stimulation (DBS) has been widely demonstrated,⁵²⁻⁵⁴ the
165 clinical and surgical expertise required for this advanced neurosurgical technique remains a
166 significant limit to its application in large urban centers. Telemedicine has the potential to curtail

167 the need for in-person follow-up visits. Two recent studies from Canada⁵⁵ and China⁵⁶ confirmed
168 the feasibility of using telemedicine for DBS in patients with PD. The number of video-guided
169 visits directly correlated to the distance between home and the DBS referral center,⁵⁵ allowing a
170 significant reduction in the logistical burden associated with travel time and costs. Both patients
171 and physicians reported a high degree of satisfaction with this interaction.⁵⁶ In all cases, technical
172 problems associated with video connections were negligible and resolved without complications.
173 Moreover, a recent study from Sweden showed that telemedicine using a video communication
174 system allows other advanced therapeutic options, such as Levodopa-carbidopa intestinal gel
175 (LCIG) infusion, at home. This approach was found to be resource-efficient, technically feasible,
176 well accepted and satisfactory by patients, neurologists, and nurses alike.⁵⁷ Similarly, the remote
177 application of tDCS showed beneficial effects in the treatment of MS-associated depression.
178 Kasschau and colleagues demonstrated the feasibility, safety, and reliability of remotely
179 supervised tDCS and reported a high adherence rate that exceeded rates of adherence of clinic-
180 based tDCS.⁵⁸

181

182 3.2.3 Telegenetics

183 The management of rare genetic disorders includes three levels of care: a) pre-diagnostic phase,
184 b) communication of the diagnosis accompanied by appropriate genetic counseling for patients
185 and family members, and c) multidisciplinary approach to deliver proper therapies and address
186 potential complications associated with disease progression.⁵⁹ Teleconsultation is a promising
187 tool to provide counseling, diagnosis, monitoring, and rehabilitation of genetic disorders to
188 satisfy these levels of care.

189 Telegenetics has the potential of limiting time and costs associated with traveling to ultra-
190 specialized tertiary referral centers and facilitate a multidisciplinary approach via roundtable
191 videoconference visits at which multiple specialists can take part.⁶⁰⁻⁶² Several studies showed the
192 potential of telegenetics as a modality to reach populations living in areas with limited access to
193 information, treatment, and psychosocial support offered by genetic services.⁶³⁻⁶⁵

194

195 3.2.4 Telediagnosis

196 The application of telemedicine to radiology has had a relatively long track record of benefits,
197 including cost-effectiveness, with pronounced concordance between conventional radiology and
198 teleradiology regarding diagnostic accuracy and reliability.⁶⁶

199 Telestroke is one of the most rapidly expanding applications of telemedicine that combines video
200 consultation, tele-radiology, and high stroke tele-expertise to provide continuous service to
201 hospitals and patients.^{67,68} Telestroke not only increases the rate of intravenous thrombolysis and
202 decisions on endovascular therapy, but also provides early triage and management of transient
203 ischemic attacks and minor strokes.^{68,69}

204 Tele-EEG, which consists in remote EEG consultation, is another application for telediagnosis in
205 neurological disorders.⁷⁰ A Canadian study showed the feasibility of telephone-based EEG-data
206 transmission.⁷¹ A more recent study proved the feasibility of tele-EEG for obtaining clinician's
207 second opinions and off-line reviews of pre-recorded data.⁷² Tele-EEG has shown to be a safe,
208 timely, and effective method for providing EEG services to underserved hospitals.^{70,73}

209 Telepathology consists of the practice of pathology by interpreting transmitted digital histologic
210 images by pathologists at a long distance.⁷⁴ In this process, the diagnosing pathologist has remote
211 but direct control over the selection and magnification of histopathology glass slides.^{75,76} A
212 recent study reported promising results from a nationwide telepathology consultation in China,
213 built to solve problems of shortage of pathologists and subspecialty pathologists at underserved
214 sites and to improve pathology quality control.⁷⁷

215

216 **3.3 New frontiers and innovative applications**

217

218 3.3.1 Telemetry

219 Telemedicine is not merely remote communication via telephone or videoconferencing but also
220 encompasses higher-order transmission of data germane to a patient's health. Telemetry, defined
221 as the "transmission of the readings of instruments to a remote location using wires, radio waves,
222 or other means," can be used to monitor patients using wearable sensors and mobile
223 applications.⁷⁸

224 Regarding the management of advanced therapies for PD, such as LCIG infusion and DBS,
225 telemetry offers a powerful tool for increasing accessibility and effectiveness of these treatments.
226 The possibility to remotely access important information such as battery consumption, electrode
227 impedance, and stimulation parameters could be useful and timely, in particular when patients
228 report sudden and inexplicable clinical worsening possibly due to battery exhaustion.⁷⁹
229 Moreover, the implementation of telemetry with objective clinical measurements through
230 wearable sensors and self-reported electronic questionnaires will increase the possibility of
231 monitoring the health status of patients, ameliorating neurological symptoms.⁸⁰ The next step in
232 the path to telemedicine and telemetry integration consists of remote intervention on DBS and
233 infusion systems programming. Jitkritisadakul and colleagues⁵⁵ recently analyzed the possibility
234 of an "indirect" intervention on DBS parameters, supervised by an expert physician through
235 video-conferencing, and physically enacted directly by the patient or caregiver or, in a minority
236 of cases, by a local physician or nurse. DBS stimulation parameters and infusion systems
237 parameters could also be modified directly from a remote location via a Bluetooth-based
238 programming system installed at the patient's home.^{56,57,81}

239 Telemetry also has applications in patients requiring intensive care, such as in the case of
240 neoplastic diseases, wherein pharmacological treatments require continuous monitoring of
241 adverse events (e.g., vomiting, dehydration, etc.) and vital signs (e.g., blood pressure, blood
242 glucose levels, pulse rate, etc.).^{82,83}

243 Regarding cerebrovascular diseases, safe administration of intravenous tissue-type plasminogen
244 activator (tPA) in acute ischemic stroke requires adherence to thrombolysis protocols that could
245 be improved through "telestroke" networks.⁶⁷ These networks assist in the interpretation of
246 neuroimaging findings⁸⁴ to assure timely selection of tPA candidates.^{85,86}

247

248 3.3.2 Telerehabilitation

249 Telerehabilitation, intended as a discipline involving remote delivery of different rehabilitation
250 services, namely speech therapy and physiotherapy, has been widely examined in neurological
251 disorders.⁸⁷ Constantinescu et al.⁸⁸ evaluated the level of agreement between online and face-to-
252 face assessment of voice disorder in patients with PD, showing that the online assessment was as
253 valid as in-person evaluations. The same authors⁸⁹, as well as a different group⁹⁰, found that

254 treatment for speech disorder is feasible and potentially applicable to innovative rehabilitation
255 techniques, such as the Lee Silverman Voice Treatment.

256 Telerehabilitation of motor functions has also been applied to PD. In a phase 1 non-randomized
257 clinical trial Ellis and coll.⁹¹ described the feasibility, acceptance, and effectiveness of a virtual
258 exercise coach to promote daily walking in community-dwelling PD patients. The study found an
259 improvement on walking speed, with good adherence to the virtual rehabilitation protocol.

260 Russell and coll.⁹² validated remote telemedicine system for the physical assessment of PD
261 patients undergoing rehabilitation.

262 Telerehabilitation may improve the level of care in patients with cancer.^{93,94} Recent studies
263 demonstrated the effectiveness of internet-based tailored exercise program for cancer survivors,
264 which may improve functional capacity and cognition,⁹⁵ as well as enhance strength and quality
265 of life reducing pain and fatigue.⁹⁶

266 Home-based telerehabilitation has also been introduced in stroke survivors, proving to be as
267 effective as traditional rehabilitation techniques.⁹⁷ Several studies showed promising results in
268 clinical,⁹⁸ kinematic,⁹⁹ and neuroimaging endpoints⁹⁷ in patients living away from health-care
269 facilities with a better cost-effectiveness profile.

270

271 **4. CHALLENGES**

272 4.1 What should be measured?

273 New possibilities in the field of telemedicine are offered by the development of wireless sensors,
274 which may be combined with videoconferencing platforms. This innovative integrated
275 technology bears the promise to dramatically change the physical assessment of patients with
276 neurological and non-neurological disorders. For example, in PD the interactive nature of clinical
277 scales conventionally used for quantification and rating of clinical symptoms (e.g., the
278 Movement Disorder Society-sponsored revision of the Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating
279 Scale)¹⁰⁰ may create a challenge to implement via telemedicine. Recent advances in wearable
280 motion sensors allowed doctors to assess some of the most disabling physical symptoms of PD
281 via videoconferencing platforms.⁴⁶ While sensors may also assist the remote monitoring of PD
282 and eliminate physicians' subjectivity in motor symptom evaluation,^{80,101} their implementation

283 into PD patients' home environment remains to be explored. In this regard, an innovative
284 platform for continuous effective assessment and monitoring of motor status in PD and other
285 neurodegenerative diseases has been recently developed to assess symptoms such as
286 bradykinesia, hypokinesia, resting tremor, rigidity, and postural instability along with
287 information provided by patients such as diet and adherence to medications.¹⁰² The ultimate goal
288 is to provide a holistic view of the patient status that might assist in the monitoring of disease
289 progression and the appropriate management of treatments.

290 In MS, the expanded disability status scale (EDSS) is the primary clinical tool currently used to
291 assess disability. The scale is time-consuming and requires a dedicated neurological exam but
292 also provides valuable information about disease progression. Researchers attempted to remotely
293 perform the EDSS neurological exam using a webcam-based approach with the patient in their
294 home environment. The ability to detect cerebellar and brainstem and sensory abnormalities
295 were inferior to hands-on EDSS.^{39,40} A modification of the scale to focus on visual observations
296 of the functions of the brainstem, the cerebellum, and the sensory system will be needed to
297 obtain comprehensive information about the patient level of disability.

298

299 4.2 Acceptability and long-term adherence

300 Regarding body-worn sensors, patient acceptability is a critical aspect. Without both physician's
301 and patient's cooperation, these systems will not be able to provide the holistic view needed to
302 increase patient monitoring. Many studies examined the accuracy of these sensor systems
303 without addressing aspects related to the comfort and acceptance of these systems. Fisher et
304 al.,¹⁰³ focused on the patient feedback found a negative correlation between prolonged wearing
305 and comfort. Still, patients wore the sensors as requested for the majority of their active day.

306 Although promising, there remains a limited number of studies evaluating the application of
307 wearable sensors in the patients' home environment for continuous monitoring.¹⁸ More studies
308 are needed to examine the long-term effect of wearable systems on patients' quality of life, as
309 well as the cost-benefit ratio of hardware and software platforms for implementation of
310 telemedicine as a standard of care.¹ Finally, the increasing ability to deliver care remotely could
311 undermine one of the most cardinal principle of medicine namely the therapeutic alliance
312 between patients and physicians.¹⁰⁴

313

314 4.3 Cost of technologies and their integration into difficult environments

315 Another challenge for the widespread diffusion of telemedicine is the cost of technologies, and
316 the difficulty of integrating them into challenging environments such as in the home of elderly
317 patients, communities with low educational status, low-middle income countries, and rural areas
318 with incomplete or absent technology penetration.¹⁰⁵ However, given the significant advantages
319 associated with the use of telehealth, further studies and applications have been advocated by
320 international societies.¹⁰⁶

321

322 **5. CONCLUSIONS**

323 Integration of telemedicine and telemetry into clinical practice represents one of the main
324 challenges of modern medicine. While widespread access to the Internet and portable
325 technologies offer the opportunity for managing complications associated with chronic
326 conditions in a home-based, patient-centered model of care, combined efforts from multiple
327 stakeholders are required to develop an interoperable software platform capable of providing not
328 only a holistic approach to care but also one that reduces disparities in the access to care in an
329 easy-to-use, secure, and cost-effective ecosystem. The limitation of this Review consists of its
330 narrative architecture; hence further systematic studies are requested to better clarify the
331 application of telemedicine to neurology.

332

333

334

335 **ABBREVIATIONS**

336

337 DBS: Deep Brain Stimulation; DMT: disease-modifying therapies; EDSS: expanded disability
338 status scale; EEG: Electroencephalogram; i.v.tPA: intravenous tissue-type plasminogen
339 activator; LCIG: Levodopa-carbidopa intestinal gel; MS: Multiple Sclerosis; PD: Parkinson's
340 disease; RCT: randomized controlled trial; tDCS: transcranial direct current stimulation.

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690 **FIGURE AND TABLE LEGENDS**

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692 **Figure 1.** Flow-chart summarizing the number of articles reviewed, those excluded, and the

693 reason of exclusion in the present study.

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695 **Figure 2.** Opportunities and challenges for telemedicine in neurological diseases.

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697 **Table 1.** Overview of the main evidences supporting the “opportunities” for telemedicine. For

698 references, see the text. PD, Parkinson Disease; DMT, disease-modifying therapies; MS,

699 Multiple Sclerosis; DBS, Deep Brain Stimulation; LCIG, Levodopa-Carbidopa Intestinal Gel;

700 tDCS, Transcranial Direct Current Stimulation; EEG, Electroencephalogram.

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730 **Figure 1.**
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755 **Figure 2.**
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781 **Table 1.**

Field of Application	Evidence
<u>Parkinson disease</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Videoconferencing may provide access to multidisciplinary medical care, reducing travel time, distance and wait time in patients with PD living in unserved areas (Pretzer-Aboff & Prettyman, 2015) • Feasibility, acceptance, and effectiveness of a virtual exercise coach to promote daily walking in community-dwelling persons with PD (Ellis et al., 2013) • Feasibility of remote physical assessment of PD patients undergoing rehabilitation (Russell et al., 2013) • Feasibility of remote evaluation and treatment of speech disorders in patients with PD (Constantinescu et al., 2010; Constantinescu et al., 2010; Howell et al., 2009)
<u>Chronic diseases and depression</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Telehealth nursing conducted by daily telemonitoring and remote sessions of problem-solving treatment for depression improve symptoms and reduce the number of emergency department visits compared to in-home nursing in elderly with chronic diseases and depression (Gellis et al., 2014)
<u>Prevention of cerebrovascular diseases</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Home blood pressure monitoring in patients with hypertension is associated with better morbidity and mortality when compared to standard office visits (Cappuccio et al., 2004; Glynn et al., 2010; Bray et al., 2010; Algawal et al., 2011; Wald et al., 2012; Stergiou et al., 2010), albeit significantly more expensive (Omboni et al., 2012) • Telemedicine may improve glycemic control and promote a healthy lifestyle in patients with types I and II diabetes mellitus (Lee et al., 2017; Bashshur et al., 2015; Health Quality Ontario, 2009)
<u>Pediatric neuro-oncology</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Videoconferencing and e-mail communications are available twinning tools between institutions in industrialized and developing countries. Twinning facilitates the implementation of multidisciplinary neuro-oncology programs in low-income countries (Qaddoumi et al., 2007, 2008, 2009; Al-Oudimat et al., 2009)
<u>Multiple sclerosis</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Telephone counseling and web-based home telehealth monitoring improves DMT adherence in patients living with MS (Turner et al., 2014) • Telephone-based, teleconference or web-based interventions are effective means to increase physical activity and improve fatigue in MS (Turner et al., 2016; Finlayson et al., 2011; Moss-Morris et al., 2012; Dlugonski et al., 2012) • Remote diagnosis and management of cognitive difficulties and depression in patients with MS (Settle et al., 2005; Mohr et al., 2007; Charvet et al., 2017) • Smartphone-based telerehabilitation has favorable effects on fatigue in MS (D'hooghe et al., 2018) • The use of virtual reality to effectively administer physiotherapy and rehabilitation to individuals living with MS (Gutiérrez et al., 2013; Paul et al., 2014)
<u>Advanced therapies (Deep brain stimulation, infusion systems, and transcranial direct current stimulation)</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feasibility of using telemedicine for DBS in patients with PD living in unserved areas (Jitkrisadakul et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2015) • Feasibility of using telemedicine for LCIG initiation in patients with PD living in unserved areas (Willows et al., 2017) • Feasibility of remotely supervised tDCS in the treatment of MS-associated depression (Kasschau et al., 2016)
<u>Stroke</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combination of video consultation, tele-radiology, and high stroke tele-expertise on a 365/24/7 basis (Wechsler et al., 2017; Dumitrascu et al., 2017) • Standard of care therapies for acute stroke are facilitated by telestroke, not only by increasing intravenous thrombolysis rates and prompt decisions on endovascular therapy, but also with early triage and management of transient ischemic attacks and minor strokes (Dumitrascu et al., 2017; Blacquiere et al., 2017)
<u>Epilepsy</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tele-EEG (remote EEG consultation) allows for better access to specialized medical care, reduces the costs and the total time associated with testing (Campos et al., 2012) • Feasibility of tele-EEG for obtaining clinician second opinions and off-line reviews of pre-recorded data (Patterson, 2005). • Tele-EEG is an achievable, safe, timely and effective method of providing EEG services to hospitals in which neurophysiological services are not available (Campos et al., 2012, Coates, 2012).

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